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INVESTIGATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL MALTREATMENT AND SEXUAL MATURATION IN BAPSI SIDHWA'S ICE-CANDY MAN: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS

Corresponding & Author:	MS. ISMA ZAHEER , Visiting Lecturer of English, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan. Email: isma.zaheer.vf@ue.edu.pk
Author 2:	DR. ASMA KHAN , Assistant Professor (English), University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan. Email: asma.khan@ue.edu.pk
Author 3:	MR. MUHAMMAD ZUBAIR , Visiting Lecturer of English, University of Sahiwal, Sahiwal, Pakistan. Email: chzubair4u@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study focuses on numerous cases of abnormal children who were sexually abused or people who were mistreated by their families. Even though this is a pressing matter, no one has paid much attention to it, not even the public. So, the focus of this research is the heroine's gradual awakening to sexuality, the pains and pleasures of adulthood, and the specific historical catastrophe. It destroys her world. (*Ice-Candy Man*, 1988). Three major components of Van Dijk's (2001) methodology are used to analyze the Socio-Cognitive Approach to Discourse (CAD). This model hypothesizes that cognition facilitates communication between the social world and discourse. Van Dijk claims Critical Discourse Analysis is of relevance to modern cognition, as certain mental models influence our perception. This type of approach is divided into three components, namely Discourse (i), Cognition (ii), and (iii) Society (Van Dijk, 2001). The main extension of this model lies in linguistics analysis, such as lexical categories. To ascertain how a child who has been abused will develop sexual maturity and what mental health problems they may experience. It aims to gain a thorough understanding of disability, sexuality, and pain-related psychological abuse. Additionally, this study will demonstrate a variety of effective strategies for eliminating all forms of psychological maltreatment. The results will help other researchers understand different ways to improve sexual or emotional abuse to get rid of all psychological abuse. So, we can say that pain causes different roles in performing different functions e.g. social, professional, and routine life.

Key Words: Maltreatment, disability, catastrophe, psychological, cognition

Introduction

Sexual development and psychological abuse are some of the most common abuses. Sexual development and psychological abuse are some of the most common abuses. They both are unified but we must not confuse them with each other. There are some differences in these terms. Psychological exploitation is as damaging as sexual misuse. It is the most damaging stage of mistreatment because it has an enormous impact on the minds of abused persons. Children who face any kind of exploitation have aftereffects during their lives. '*Sexual Maturity*' is the capacity of the persons who want to achieve their sexual desires. It has three different stages: (i) biological maturity, (ii) physical maturity, and (iii) psychological maturity. On the other hand, '*Emotional Maturity*' is the response to meet the necessities of certain conditions. If a person is sensually developed, he will also be emotionally developed as well. (Schneiders, p. 435).

Background of Study:

In ancient civilizations, child abuse has a very shameful history. It is still a dominant subject in the modern times. Although child abuse is always a neglected subject, we should break the chains of silence and focus on this burning issue. The most common consequences of child abuse are trauma, chaos, nervousness, depression, and unhappiness. Abused children have to face all these challenges throughout their lives. Here we will elaborate on child sexual abuse in the context of disability. How sexual maturity and psychological maltreatment are interrelated to each other?

Problem Statement:

This research focuses on the gradual coming of a disabled child heroin to sexuality, the pains and joys of adulthood, and the historical disaster that disrupts her life. It also examines the traumatic consequences of psychological abuse, the sexual development process, and the emotional distress of an

abnormal life. The purpose of this study is to identify the mental health issues of an abused child who tells a story during the partition. Before the historical disaster, Lenny's life was not so miserable.

Research Objectives

This paper aims:

- To identify the primary causes and their consequences on individuals who have been subject to psychological abuse.
- To gain an in-depth understanding of disability, sexuality, and psychological trauma associated with pain.
- To demonstrate how individuals with disabilities cope with everyday life and interactions with others.
- To examine the characters' perspectives of sexuality and grief on humanity to gain insight into their mental state.

Research Questions:

1. How do we explore the various motivations and consequences of physical and emotional aggression on individuals through Sidhwa's characterization?
2. What are the major consequences on the daily lives and interactions of individuals with disabilities and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) considering Sidhwa's Lenny character after the partition?
3. What are the enormous impacts of pain to sexual and emotional abuse experienced by Shanta and Dilnawaz?

Significance and Scope:

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the role of emotional responses in the sexual and emotional development of abnormal children following the physical manipulation act of manipulating the body part of someone. This work will be of great value to those researchers who are still struggling and those who lack the courage to overcome their grief. Additionally, this study will demonstrate a variety of effective strategies for eliminating all forms of psychological maltreatment. So, A Socio-cognitive approach is applied to this study to

elaborate on the significance of the research (Van Dijk, 2001).

Literature Review

RJ Cooper discussed the concept of grief and the desire of humans to understand the causes of their suffering in the world since the beginning of human existence. Humans must seek answers to better comprehend the processes that aid in the acceptance of loss. This paper examines how grief, suffering, and pain affect literary studies and how various critics attempt to address the inherent and enigmatic nature of grief, which can be either sexual or emotional (Cooper, 2000).

Definitions:

Psychological Abuse:

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, Abuse is any kind of behavior in which we mistreat someone with cruelty. So, the other names for psychological abuses are intellectual misuse, psychological violence, expressive exploitation, etc. Although there are so many kinds of abuses it is the most common type among all sorts of abuses. It is very harmful as it compels the abuser to think about negative things that he cannot do anything about. Abusers use foul language to reveal their aggression. A victim feels embarrassment while facing another individual due to damaging fears. A victim always remains silent and does not contact other people. In short, it is a set of unhealthy activities. It is very hard to recognize this kind of abuse as it occurs in someone's thoughts. It is so severe abuse because our close relationships e.g., friends, members of the family, colleagues, etc. are also unable to recognize these *symptoms* (Maggie Wooll, 2021).

The major signs of psychological abuse are:

- (i) Hopelessness:** A person who is suffering from mental illness always remains upset. He feels as he is powerless and helpless.
- (ii) Refusal to Communication:** A victim of this kind of abuse does not communicate with anyone and always remains silent.

(iii) Nervousness: This abuser feels scared while facing certain individuals. He frequently feels frightened as well as ashamed.

(iv) Unusual Behaviors: This person does not behave in a normal way. He behaves in an unfamiliar way e.g., offensive talking, and eating in a very bad manner.

(v) Questions the existence: Due to the traumatic incidents of partition, Bapsi's character Mumtaz condemns himself and questions his reality.

(vi) Isolation: It attempts to isolate a person from his friends or members of his family. The abuser does not like get-togethers (Sanjana Gupta, 2023).

Psychological maltreatment is characterized by a range of symptoms. It includes anxiety, persistent depression, anxiety-related stress, denial, intimidation, an authority imbalance, dysfunction, and slurs. The definition of emotional or psychological abuse is provided in the following quotation: "Psychological abuse is the sustained, repetitive, inappropriate behavior which damages or substantially reduces the creative and developmental potential of crucially important mental faculties and mental processes of a child, including intelligence, memory, recognition, perception, attention, imagination, and moral development." (Kieran O'Hagan, 1992).

Sexual Maturation or Sexual Abuse

Sexual maturation is a fundamental stage of human development, which varies from individual to individual. It is largely determined by one's genetic makeup, and environmental factors can have a major influence on it. Generally, sexual maturation is divided into four main stages: (i) Gender assignment, (ii) gender identification, (iii) school age, (iv) ages six to twelve, (v) adolescence, (vi) young adulthood, (vii) adulthood (viii), late adulthood, etc. The two main topics covered in Sidhwa's book are the exploitation of women and sexual assault

victimization. It appears an important biological indication is sexual development. It has a great influence on the lives of children. In the novel, *'Ice-Candy Man'*, we perceive sexual maturity in Bapsi's character Lenny. During the partition of the Sub-continent, she has to go through different stages of sexual growth e.g., the love story of Ayah. Generally, women are portrayed as having been deliberately assaulted and neglected. In short, sexualization is the basic term in this study. It is associated with mutual psychological strength. Women who face sexual abuse during their childhood have multiple impacts on their mental health.

These are the five major types of sexual abuse:

(i) Verbal Sexual Abuse: A kind of abuse in which we torture someone verbally. It occurs in social settings e.g., homes and workplaces. It is very hard to deal with this kind of abuse due to our lifeblood relations. The main examples are name-calling, sexual description of images sexual jokes, and offensive language.

(ii) Convert Sexual Abuse: A kind of misuse in which teases another person without any knowledge e.g., bullying. It attempts to get the attention of another person. For example: If a person is not willing for sexual activities and we are teasing someone for sexual pleasures.

(iii) Visual Sexual Abuse: A kind of exploitation in which someone is tortured by showing different unwanted images and undesirable acts e.g., nude movies.

(iv) Physical Sexual Abuse: A kind of mistreatment in which there is an unwanted touch with the next person e.g., kissing and touching.

(v) Ritualistic Sexual Abuse: It is a mixture of spirituality as well as rites e.g., child marriages. Usually, it talks about what our religion says about ritual sexual abuse (Cristina Ally, 2020).

Sexual Maturation and Psychological Abuse

in Sidhwa's "Ice-Candy Man"

The main purpose of conducting this research is to study the notions of sexual development and psychological abuse. These terminologies are going to be studied in light of Sidhwa's characters in *'Ice-Candy Man'*. It is a historical fiction in which Sidhwa explores the *'complex trauma of sexual development'* during the childhood of the protagonist. Child protagonist Lenny has to go through different phases of adult life. It shows the embodiments of her infant. Lenny has different levels of human emotions as a child. She has seen different consequences of partitions e.g., deaths of innocent people, the love affair between Shanta and Ice-Candy Man, the rape of innocent girls by Hindu Sikhs, etc. Consequently, to recognize the mental health problems that the abused children who tell the story during the partition are dealing with, as this has a big impact on their lives.

Earlier studies on Bapsi Sidhwa's "Ice-Candy Man"

In this section, the investigators will be delving into the various studies that have previously been conducted on the phenomenon of the Ice-Candy Man. A selection of these studies is provided below:

Syrrina Ahsan Ali Haq's article entitled *'Dialectic of Identity Through the Parsee Narrator'*, says that although there are many ways to interpret the division of India and Pakistan, dialogue is one of them. Bapsi Sidhwa concentrates on the perspective of the Parsee Community throughout the novel's significance of dialogue in some way (Ice-Candy Man, 1988).

In the Journal, a study was published about religion, partition, identity, and the Diaspora in the South Asian sub-continent. The study was conducted using a child narrator to explore the partition history. It also discussed how migrations caused difficulties for the living population of the area. During the period of separation between India and Pakistan, there was a great deal of bloodshed

and violence. No one cared for each other, and all were in a state of poverty. Women were subject to physical and mental exploitation, and all things and people were subjected to torture ([Promita Deb, 2011](#)). In "Ice Candy Man", we witness the persecution of Hindus and Muslims, with many being expelled, robbed, and raped. This was one of the most difficult political periods in the history of India. On the other hand, "Train to Pakistan" proves that people are inherently sincere and humane.

Additional Relative Studies:

Child Physical Abuse:

This paper reviews various papers on the topic of non-accidental head injuries and physical abuse against children. It offers a qualified evaluation of the likelihood that parents of children who have been referred to child and adolescent psychiatry will physically abuse those children. Additionally, the paper reviews other relevant research on the topic of bodily misuse of children. This research is interlinked with the current research, as they both have similar themes.

Significant Effects on Victims' Academic Performance:

This research at Pennsylvania University Park examined the effects of physical punishment on kids' academic performance. It was discovered that physical abuse had a significant impact on kids' cognitive abilities. Kids would suffer if it did not go down often completed in a state of extreme isolation. Performance and classroom engagement were linked to the environment of the child's home, such as how they were treated at home, whether it was kind or harsh. After the partition of the sub-continent, Lenny could not continue her study. If the child was subjected to severe punishment, it would lead to a decrease in their personality traits due to the carelessness of their caregivers. The study examined three types of physical punishment: mild corporal abuse which is harsh and abusive. A drop in

academic performance was linked to all types of physical abuse ([Brooke McCord, 2017](#)).

Abnormal pain from pressure:

'Autism Spectrum Disorder' is interconnected with the emotional abuse faced by Lenny's character. This piece provides evidence that youngsters who suffer from 'autism spectrum disorders (ASD) tend to demonstrate an unusual response to tactile cues compared to wholesome children. The purpose of the study is to investigate the sensory and motor functions of children with ASD through impartial testing methods. The upper limbs, lips, and hands of high-functioning ASD kids were evaluated in comparison to those of upper-class children. The results of the study indicated that children with ASD exhibited increased pain and sensitivity compared to those of healthy children ([I. Riquelme, 2016](#)).

Child abuse and neglect have negative effects:

This project was conducted by [Petersen A., Joseph J, and Feit M, \(2014\)](#) in Washington, D.C. It offers a fresh viewpoint on child abuse and neglect. These two forms of abuse, e.g., psychological and sexual are social experiences and can have a detrimental effect on the capacity to trust caregivers. So, the children at this stage often have interpersonal issues ([Joseph & Feit, 2014](#)).

Psychological Harm:

Child abuse and neglect can take many different forms, ranging from physical and sexual abuse to emotional and just neglect in meeting the needs of the child. These conditions can lead to severe psychological harm for the child. A classic example of this is the Case study of a 12-year-old orphan boy who suffered physical and mental distress after being physically abused by a family member. He must face different emotional abuses for the rest of his life ([Kemoli,2018](#)). Despite much research on Ice Candy Man, the exact mechanisms behind many themes remain unclear. Two of these are sexual

maturation and psychological abuse discussed in actual settings. It extracts new topics like the coatings of human conduct. By using critical discourse analysis, the understanding of many different societal problems e.g., social standards, and supremacy are also discussed in this study. The concerned study can focus on how literature repeats and changes our understanding of difficult themes by critically examining the story.

Research Techniques

In this study, a socio-cognitive approach to discourse is applied. It is also called the Event or Complex model. According to Van Dijk, cognition is essentially the true representation of the discourse. Discourse and cognition, both are running side by side. In this theory, Van Dijk explains how social settings affect our manuscript and discussions. This model has three major dimensions: (i) *Discourse*, (ii) *Cognition*, and (iii) *Society*. Mostly, this model deals with the relationship between text and society in light of cognition. He says textual and social constructions are facilitated by social cognition. (Van Dijk, 2001),

See Appendices A, B, C, D and E

Analysis

The foremost aim of this study is to investigate the different methods of characterization through the lens of qualitative and descriptive analysis. In this study, the '*Socio-Cognitive Approach to Discourse*' by Van Dijk is also functional (Van Dijk, 2001). This study talks about how to cope with sorrow. It can be of different types. We cannot declare death as a cause of grief. Grief can also occur after sexual violence, bodily ferocity as well as any sort of child abuse. According to research, grief has five basic stages: (i) rejection, (ii) rage, (iii) negotiating, (iv) hopelessness, and (v) acceptance (Kubler-Ross, 2022). So, we can say that it is a character examination in which we have to investigate different characters. Character's part in the story, their connection with other

members, and their effects on others as an individual, all are the elementary goals of this study.

Descriptive and Qualitative Research:

Different characteristics of qualitative and descriptive research are applied to Sidhwa's characterization of 'Ice-Candy Man' because they have some common features linked with the novel.

Qualitative Research:

The major focus in qualitative research is placed on social inquiry. It also talks about how a person analyzes the events that he/she has experienced in their daily life. This kind of study includes a comprehensive description of data. It is customarily stated in descriptions, arguments, and items. It is prolonged and contains a personal conclusion. We conclude disorganized data as researchers. It always answers three questions: (i) how, (ii) what, and (iii) why in our summaries. There are different steps in this study e.g., the statement of the problem, the main purpose of research, three main research questions, research methodology, data collection, data analysis, and result interpretation (Yilmaz, 2013).

Descriptive Research:

This study involves a complete investigation of a detailed spectacle. It can be in the form of individuals or groups, a setting, or a society. So, the main goal behind this research is to detect and record the situations and proceedings. In addition to accurately describing the subject of study, it aims to provide answers to what, when, where, and how questions. It sheds light on the nature of the issue. Data is gathered through surveys or in-person interviews. The following steps make up the research process: problem statement, information identification, data selection, target population/sample, information collection method, data analysis, and generalizations (H Taherdoost, 2021).

The Traumatic Effects of Partition on the People during Migration:

Sexual Maturation:

Sidhwa portrays the sexual development of Lenny’s character. This paper focuses on the gradual coming to her sexuality as an adult, the challenges and rewards of adulthood, and the historical catastrophe that upsets her world. A crucial aspect of human existence, sexual maturation differs from person to person. [Cavanagh, R. J. \(1970\)](#) Sexual maturation can be divided into four main stages: (i) gender assigned and gender identification, (ii) school-age children or children between the ages of six and twelve, (iii) adolescents, young adults, and (iv) adults and late adults. Sidhwa accurately depicted the sexual development of a teenage girl Lenny, in question throughout the novel. The exploitation of women and the victimization of women by sexual violence are the book's main themes. There have been intentional raped and exploitation of women. In light of the socio-cognitive model, various examples of sexual maturation include:

The following examples that illustrate the subject of sexuality are taken directly from the text. As a result, it is simple to understand Lenny's sexual maturation stages.

Character description of Shanta:

Shanta, also known as Mumtaz or Ayah, is a brilliant, beautiful, and responsible woman who is Lenny's mentor. Despite her religious differences, she is adored by many. The partition of India has had a profound effect on her life, and she is one of the easy victims of the angry Muslims, who raped her. She is later married to Ice Candy Man, who keeps her in a place known for its dancing girls. This marriage is a betrayal of Ice Candy Man's love for Ayah, which extinguishes her dreams and ultimately destroys her soul. Towards the end of the film, she begs her godfather to send her away to Amritsar, leading to a bittersweet conclusion. [\(Ice-Candy Man, pg. 44\).](#)

<u>Discourse</u>	<u>Cognition</u>	<u>Society</u>
This text provides insight into the feminist perspective on the female psyche and its associated experiences, as exemplified by the narrative of H.G. Wells' novel "The Doors in the Wall" (Well,2018).	The concept of 'cognition' is explored in various works of literature, such as the play "Hamlet" by William Shakespeare, in which the protagonist, Ophelia, is emotionally tormented by her lover's decision to send her to a mental institution, known as "Hira Mandi"	This text is a representation of the oppression of women in modern society, as evidenced by the use of the term "yellow wallpaper" by Charlotte Perkins Gilman in 1892.

Admirers of Shanta:

Ayah has a captivating and luxurious figure, which has attracted a large following, which included beggars, old men, holy men, the ice-candy man, and young men. These admirers are all enthralled by Ayah's curvaceous form. As we are aware. She is Lenny's "Ayah.", the Sexual Maturation process of Lenny begins when he sees all his admirers. [\(Ice-Candy Man, pg. 44\).](#)

<u>Cognition</u>	<u>Society</u>
This text illustrates the development of Lenny's sexual maturity and the experiences of Ayah's romantic partners (Teun van Dijk, 2001) in light of the theories developed by Freud in 1899.	This text illustrates different individuals in society. Keeping in view the topic of sex, contemplate it, and perpetrate acts of rape to satisfy their physical desires, as exemplified by the case of Zainab in the context of Qasoor.

The Pains of Abnormal Life

The theme of disability is clearly stated in Lenny's character. So, the consequences of an abnormal life have had a profound effect on the individuals affected by any form of illness. We have selected this paper to focus exclusively on the theme of disability in the context of our novel. The definition of disability is the state of being disabled. It primarily causes permanent harm. It might have come about by accident or by birth. According to research, it has multiple causes: arthritis, heart disease, and stroke (Sruthi M, 2022). The World Health Organization estimates that there are 15% disabled persons in the world's population. So according to the Statistics, the disability ratio in Pakistan is 6.2% (Rubab Meraj, 2023).

Findings

The following outcomes are predicted:

- Due to its rarity, psychological abuse can have a significant negative impact on the physical and mental health of the victim. Lenny loses her senses when she comes to know about the miseries of prostitutes.
- One of the consequences of psychological abuse is a decrease in self-esteem as we have elaborated in Shanta's character.
- Poor self-esteem can be the outcome of any exploitation e.g., depression. Exploitation of women is perceived throughout Bapsi's characterization e.g., Ayah as a dancing girl after the partition of the sub-continent.
- An abused person cannot express himself in front of others due to stress and fear. Shanta is unable to express her emotions for Mumtaz in Hira Mandi.
- A person with a sexual disability has a lack of interest in sex. Lenny is suffering from a physical disability. So, she has a lack of interest in sexual activities.

To sum up, individuals have different causes and consequences of psychological abuse in their lives. The shocking possessions of partition can be acknowledged in the form

of pain, disability, and grief faced by different characters.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to determine the mental health problems that children who have experienced elder abuse, domestic violence, and other types of abuse are dealing with. Because many cases of abuse at home remain unspeakable, it is important to note that child abuse is still taboo in Pakistan. A lot of research has been done recently to investigate the different types of mental health problems that kids can have, like loneliness, anxiety, and fear. The goal of this study is to identify the psychological issues that child abusers deal with. Who are sharing the experiences they had during the partition and any other problems they might have had in life. (i) It is essential to identify and address mental health issues that have been exploited. We can identify different mental health issues by these symptoms e.g., isolation, depression, helplessness, anxiety, and lack of appetite. (ii) The government should adopt measures to address and prevent this issue by opening different rehabilitation centers. (iii) If a young person experiences sexual abuse, we should support them because life is full of opportunities, and no one is ever at a standstill. (iv) The most effective way to survive is to let go and move on. (v) These individuals are characterized by their sensitivity and can experience a wide range of emotions that can be easily triggered.

Recommendations

This research gives further dimensions for future researchers in multiple ways:

- (i) to reveal all those persons who are suffering from any sort of disability, who are being sexually abused or raped, who are in favor of inter-community marriages
- (ii) to cope with grief and learn to heal,
- (iii) people can recover from the loss of their loved ones,
- (iv) Students gain basic knowledge about the

- thematic study of the novel,
 (v) to use different strategies to express their personality after the loss and the traumatic effects of partition.

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Appendix A

SOCIO-COGNITIVE MODEL		EXTENSION IN MODEL	
<p><u>Discourse</u> Intimate interaction, written content, associated gestures, images, and the semantic dimension of meaning is two. separate components of this communication event. It consists of two things: Discourse structure: It goes beyond the discourse framework through Bapsi’s characterization, describing and illuminating the discourses. construction, such as knowledge, attitude, or ideology. Ideological Discourse Structure: It focuses on the goals of their activities for instance: public servants for society (Journalists), imparting knowledge (professors), and saving nature (environmentalists). (Van Dijk, 2001)</p>	<p><u>Cognition</u> The notion of cognitive function encompasses thought, intelligence, reason, and consciousness. It can encompass both personal and social. cognitive processes, such as beliefs, objectives, evaluations, and emotions. It is composed of three sub-categories: 1. Memory (which is a component of the human mind and comprises two distinct parts: short-term and long-term memory). For example: the destruction of the partition. 2. Mental Models Mental Models are multi-dimensional. individualized, and one-of-a-kind (e.g., action, occurrences, objectives, contexts, and experiences). Different prevailing situations of the character’s mind throughout the novel. (ii) Social Cognition The concept of Social Cognition encompasses the following elements: (i) Knowledge: the ability to interact with others in a social setting. Being a member of society, Lenny has to interact with people. (ii) Attitudes: The survey examined attitudes. (Van Dijk, 2001)</p>	<p><u>Society</u> Socio-political situations usually influence language. So, it encompasses both interpersonal contact and social and political structures, such as groups, governments, organizations, and cultures. It also encompasses the primary social components, such as power and dominance. The primary social component that demonstrates dominance is that of organizations, institutions, nations, and businesses. Leaders and symbolic elites, on the other hand, demonstrate power using political, media, educational, cultural, and corporate entities. (Van Dijk, 2001).</p>	<p><u>Wodak Meyer on 29 July 2015</u> The sociological cognitive approach is based on Discourse components, cognitive components, and social components that make up the three dimensions. Based on the context, the integration of the components is the main improvement to the model in this study. This implies that, when viewed in the context of racism, the components form an organization of individuals from different groups, such as races. This is a key characteristic of a multidimensional approach. In 2018, the primary extension is to identify the lexical category and Lexical density for a few key characters from the book as shown in the table below.</p>

Appendix B

CHARACTER DESCRIPTION LEXICAL CATEGORIES	Lexical Classes				LANGUAGE DENSITY
<p>Lenny: In this novel, the protagonist is an eight-years old Parsi girl who is essentially a child narrator. Her narrative begins in her fifth year and culminates in her eighth birthday, during which she is afflicted with a disability. She has a profound effect on her life due to her disability. Lenny's residence in Lahore, broke out a disturbance resulting in a violence, and the death of innocent people. Lenny's disappointment and misfortune, which is ultimately resolved with an external realism that is both bitter and unbearable (<i>Ice-Candy Man, 1988</i>).</p>	<p><u>Noun</u> Nouns can be used as a source of information, such as the name of a person, a place, or a concept. They can also be used to represent subjects. For instance, Lenny, Nightingale, Jail Road, Warri's Road, Canal, and Morang Chungi are all examples of the source of information. Other examples include the narrator, Birdman, Hira Mandi.</p>	<p><u>Verb</u> The use of language to describe an event, phenomenon, or state of being can be illustrated by a variety of examples, such as borrowing, screening, confusing, cracking, initiating, maintaining, and observing. All of these examples demonstrate a certain type of some sort, whether it be an action or a state of being.</p>	<p><u>Adjective</u> An adjective is a term used to describe or characterize. Regardless of whether it is positive or negative. Examples of adjectives include: 'Polio stricken', 'girl child', 'self-indulgence', 'deformity', 'Reshaped foot', 'physical wealth', 'status protected', 'Parsi attitude', 'Leg braces', 'Grow up', etc.</p>	<p><u>Adverb</u> Adverbs are a type of verbal expression that convey information about the context, setting, and time. Examples of such terms include "bad", "submissive", "princess", "ally", "sexual," "Intimate," "nightmares" "bitter," and "slowly"</p>	<p>An online grading app can be used to calculate the lexical density. It is used to separate your text into individual sentences and then individual words as well. It is also used to determine the likelihood of different words. This density is essentially a measure of the quantity of a category. For example, the dictionary density is 30%, the verb density is 13%, the adjective density is 9.4% and the adverb density is 4.8%</p>

Appendix C

<p>Shanta: Mumtaz, also known as Ayah, is a brilliant, beautiful, and responsible woman who is Lenny's mentor. Despite her religious differences, she is adored by a large number of people. Partition has had a profound effect on her life, and she is one of the easy victims of the angry Muslims, who rape her. She is later married to Ice Candy Man, who keeps her at a place frequented by dancing girls. This marriage is a betrayal of Ice Candy Man's love for Ayah, which extinguishes her dreams and destroys her soul. Towards the end of the film, Mumtaz pleads with her Godmother to transport her and her family to Amritsar, thus concluding the narrative</p>	<p>Examples of such words include: Lenny, Ayah, The Villager, Inspector General, Ice Candy Man, Hakeem, Gowel-Mandi, Sharbat Khan, Nursemaid, Chawk Bazaar, Ranna Village, Rodabi, Baray Mian, etc. These words function as a source of information, strength, or authority</p>	<p>Examples of such words include: 'beginning', 'name', 'drawing', , 'strange', 'masked', 'pushing', 'spending', ', 'cracking' and 'apprehension'</p>	<p>Examples of such words include "sharp", "chocolate brown," "maternal", "responsible", "Similar" and "differing", "cheerful", "proud", "desperate", "hopeless", "ruin" and "Dancing girls"</p>	<p>The following are examples: "hopeful, deftly, wide, victory," "strictly, shapely," "relatively," "painful bunions, "indefatigable", "tasteless," "dependable", "Adults," etc. These are all verb modifiers</p>	<p>The density of words in the dictionary ranges from 28.11% for nouns to 13.7% for verbs, and 7.09% for adjectives to 5.3%</p>
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Appendix D

<p>Ice-Candy-Man: Dilnawaz is the protagonist of the novel because the entire narrative centers around him. As his mother was present in the area when he was a child, he developed his personality to suit his tastes. He is fond of Shanta and is a talented poet, reciting Urdu verses to her. He does an odd job of freeing birds. During the partition, he makes her lover Ayah work as a prostitute. He becomes jealous as he sees so many men moving around Ayah due to her beauty (<i>Ice-Candy Man, 1988</i>).</p>	<p>Examples of such terms include "Lahore", "Pakistan", "Ghand ijee", "Objection", "Ayah", "Hindu woman", "Dilnawaz", "Shanta", "Pindo", "Hira Mandi", and others.</p>	<p>Examples of such terms include: "pimping," "changing," "inspired", "determine", "maddening", "abstracted," "amazed," and "started". All of these terms indicate some form of action</p>	<p>Examples of this can be found in the terms "wild, brute, terrible, lusty, "admirer," "efficient livelihood," "Dancing girls", "Frenzied anxiety," "madman", and "screaming". All of these terms, by referencing a single word, demonstrate the characteristics of that word.</p>	<p>Examples of such terms include spoonful. definitely. polite; lungi hardly. uncommonly, secretly. squatted; and crankily. All of these terms are verb modifiers.</p>	<p>The density of words in the dictionary ranges from 28.7% for nouns, 13.5% for verbs, 7.08% for adjectives, and 4.5% for adverbs</p>
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Appendix E

<p>Godmother: She is the grandmother of Lenny. She is a very wise woman among all Sethi's family. Her good name is Roda. Lenny considers Roda as her role model. She helped Ayah when she was working as a prostitute. When she sees the sexual ferocity in culture, she challenges herself to encounter it. In our society, different girls are forced to become prostitutes for the sake of their livelihood. Finally, she is an independent lady in Sidhwa's novel (<i>Ice-Candy Man, 1988</i>).</p>	<p>Examples of such terms include Hira Mandi, Giri Mandi, Grandma Mandi, Kotha Mandi, Rodabi Mandi, Slave sister, Gurpura, Warris Road, Rape, Prey, etc. These terms provide a description of a person, object,</p>	<p>Examples of what constitutes an action or a state of being include: suppression, awareness, development, overlap, humming, whispering, addiction, presentation, and the like</p>	<p>Examples of such terms include: 'cut throat', 'dancing-girls', 'drunk', 'butcher', 'shameless badmash', 'unfaithful', 'namak-khram', 'center-stage', and 'contagion'</p>	<p>Examples include Fully, Shabbily, Purposefully, Personally, Extremely, Emotionally, Unjustly, Properly, Simultaneously, Realistically etc. These are all verb modifiers</p>	<p>The density of the language is 20.6% for nouns, 7.06% for verbs, 4.5% for adjectives, and 3% for adverbs</p>
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